

THE ROLE OF MASS MEDIA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

Dadasheva Akida Abdujabbarovna

Professor of the Department of public international law, Doctor of Law,
Tashkent State Transport University, Uzbekistan

E-mail: aqida777@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to analyze the place of media in the development of civil society in Uzbekistan. Media in civil society (media) as a democratic institution as the main guarantees of self-government of society is the content analysis of the legislation of Uzbekistan. In civil society, the focus is on a general and specific analysis of international and national media documents. As a result, tasks were developed to further strengthen the role and role of the media in the system of institutions of civil society, to ensure the constitutional rights of citizens to freedom of speech and freedom of choice.

Keywords: informed society, media, civil society, democratic Institute, free speech, data acquisition, political-spiritual awareness, copyright.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century, called the information age by the world community, is characterized by its intensity, speed, and richness in news. Especially citizenship, according to some scientists, in an informed society, the need for information becomes more intense. The reason is that in such a society, citizens receive information regarding the activities of state authorities and governing bodies without any obstacles and freely use them. After all, the view that today the owner of information – a person who can trace, find, create, analyze and disseminate information-also owns the world, has risen to the level of reality. It is now positive that the media, participating as the fourth power in developed countries, can openly express an impartial opinion on the activities of the government and deliver full-fledged deliveries to citizens. From direct, that is, direct forms of public control, the participation of citizens in the management of the affairs of society through the local self-governing bodies, citizens' assemblies, public hearings is important. We can see that the role and role of the media in scientific research has been much emphasized by the wide scope, importance.

MAIN PART

The study of public opinion as a means by which the media can articulate the opinion of citizens is an obligation imposed on NGOs, citizens' self-government bodies and public bodies if they have the right to the media. This obligation arises from the responsibility of public bodies and officials to society and citizens and provides for the effective organization of Public Administration. As you know, Mass Management is two – sided: straight-consists of public bodies to those they control, as well as return information flows, the opposite of which is true. The effectiveness of public administration depends on the possibility of obtaining unbiased, complete and useful information, that is, return communications. Public opinion is a useful piece of information as it unites and represents the interests of the majority, and its study and consideration is one of the demands for effective governance and democracy. So, according to the current legislative acts, public opinion can be independently studied by state bodies themselves, as well as use in this the final documents of public opinion, the results of other forms of public participation, which are surrounded by subjects of public control.

In modern civilization, news or information about various events and phenomena is delivered through the media. As you know, the media includes television, radio, newspapers, magazines, the Internet, etc [6; 7; 8; 9; 10; 11; 12; 13].

In civil society, the media as a democratic institution is one of the main guarantees of self-government of society. In addition to fulfilling the function of communicating information to members of society and providing them with information, they are also important in overcoming existing problems in society. They also influence that decisions made by the authorities as an independent political force are in harmony with the interests of society. It is necessary to note that democracy, when applied to the field of information, primarily refers to information pluralism (diversity), freedom of expression, non-censorship, and the recognition of the media as the "fourth authority".

Professor of law J.Abdullaev believes that the media is not directly engaged in the creativity of law, but without the participation of this institute, it is difficult to imagine activities related to the preparation and implementation of important regulatory legal acts of state bodies. Consequently, together with political parties, public and non-governmental organizations, they are tasked with creating a social balance as an intermediary in the system of relations between the state and the people. [3. 14-19]

Such mediation is undoubtedly beneficial for both parties. Media-mediated feedback with power is introduced, that is, delivering its point of view to the people, receiving unbiased information about the situation in society and the public's attitude towards the decisions of authorities, while the population, in turn, receives information

about the policy of institutions of power in one case or another and, to some extent, influences its essence through the media.

Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of human rights states that "...freedom to seek, obtain and disseminate information and ideas by any means, regardless of state boundaries"[1] is stated. The principle of freedom of media in our country, the right to ban censorship and monopolization of information, to receive information, to process and distribute it, to think and to freedom of expression are enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The relevant legislative framework for the implementation of freedom of speech and media has been formed, including such laws as "on the media" (in the new edition), "on guarantees and freedom of information", "on the principles and guarantees of freedom of information", "on public control", "on the protection of journalistic activities". The fact that the freedom to think and express it can be limited by law only if it concerns the secret of the state and other secrets is expressed in our basic law.

In order to ensure the openness, transparency, timely and complete presentation of information about the activities of public authorities and governing bodies, the websites of all public bodies operate.

However, it is impossible to ignore the fact that other information on the internet has a low level of reliability, which is reflected in the consciousness and spirituality of citizens.

Moreover, it is no secret that cybercrime is gaining momentum today. In particular, criminal acts such as the theft of money from banks over the Internet, the capture of valuable information, the preparation and dissemination of illegal information are observed.

It should be noted that in a rapidly changing turbulent time – without being indifferent and careless in the information age, but rather living with a touch of events happening around us, uncompromising in relation to dangerous plagues that are regaining their heads in different regions of the world, fighting against the manifestations of "mass culture", the words of the bot-bot-bots are not just calls today. Former US President Jimmy Carter did not in vain state that "the \$ 1 spent on propaganda is more effective than the \$ 10 spent on arms".

Therefore, the concept put forward by the head of the Republic indicated that the following issues related to the further development of the media of Uzbekistan would be resolved. These are: economic mechanisms for controlling media activity, the closeness of information sources, as well as problems related to the elimination of certain levels of pressure on editorial offices by authorities and administrative formations [2].

The implementation of the above measures will help to further strengthen the role and role of media in the system of institutions of civil society, to more fully realize the constitutional rights of citizens aimed at ensuring freedom of speech and freedom of choice [4; 5].

CONCLUSION

Based on the above, we would like to note that they pay special attention to the following tasks:

First, it is important to understand that, following the Eastern philosophy of life, obtaining quality-based information in the educational process has its collection, use, effective and important aspects and bring it to young people;

Secondly, to train our citizens to think through the cultivation of their political-spiritual consciousness and thinking, to expand their worldview is an urgent task of today. Because subjugation because of non-thinking is a thousand times more tragic than subjugation by force;

Thirdly, it is important that every citizen who uses copyright in the Republican media make speeches without forgetting the responsibility of the word;

Fourth, in the process of carrying out the above tasks, it is necessary to be selfless every day, every hour, to study ourselves in a tireless, tireless science towards Great Goals, to make this quality a criterion for our constant, daily activities

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